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**Magnetite-binding proteins from the magnetotactic bacterium
Desulfamplus magnetovallimortis BW-1**

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This library contains the results from the tertiary structure prediction with RaptorX and I-Tasser as well as the plasmid sequences (incl. results from DNA sequencing). It further contains the raw images from SDS-PAGE as well as the results of the quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation (QCMD) measurements and the X-ray diffraction (XRD) experiments.

1. Tertiary structure prediction

The sequences of the full length Mad proteins were used for tertiary structure prediction with RaptorX (<http://raptorx.uchicago.edu/ContactMap/>) and I-Tasser (<https://zhanggroup.org/I-TASSER/>).

The reports <Mad_Website.pdf> as well as the obtained .pdb files <Mad_Download> can be found in the respective folders for each Mad protein. For both predictions, model 1 is shown in the supporting information of the manuscript (Fig. S1-S11).

2. Plasmid sequences

The subfolders for each respective plasmid contain the full plasmid sequence in both .fasta and gene bank (.gb) format. The subfolders further contain the results from DNA sequencing with the primers T7 (forward; TAATACGACTCACTATAGGG) and T7term (reverse; CTAGTTATTGCTCAGCGGT). The results are provided as .txt files. In addition, .pdf files with the chromatograms are included.

3. SDS-PAGE

The uncropped raw images are included as .tif files and are organized as described below:

<MadProteinsAll.tif> shows the SDS-PAGE (15%, reducing conditions) of all purified proteins (Fig. S12). For each sample, 5 µg of total protein was used. The following samples were loaded from left to right:

- empty
- empty
- size marker (New England Biolabs, Unstained Protein Marker, Broad Range, #P7702)
- empty
- sfGFP-Mad3-His
- sfGFP-Mad4-His
- sfGFP-Mad5-His
- sfGFP-Mad8-His
- sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His
- sfGFP-Mad10-His
- sfGFP-Mad11-His
- sfGFP-His
- empty
- size marker (New England Biolabs P7702)
- empty

<Mad10trunc_Native.tif> shows the SDS-PAGE (18%, reducing conditions) of the purification of His-Mad10trunc and Mad10trunc-His under native conditions (Fig. S13). The following samples were loaded from top to bottom:

- His-Mad10trunc – insoluble fraction of the crude extract
- His-Mad10trunc – soluble fraction of the crude extract
- His-Mad10trunc – flow through
- His-Mad10trunc – wash with loading buffer
- His-Mad10trunc – washing buffer I
- His-Mad10trunc – washing buffer II
- His-Mad10trunc – eluted protein
- size marker (New England Biolabs, P7719S)
- Mad10trunc-His – eluted protein
- Mad10trunc-His – washing buffer II
- Mad10trunc-His – washing buffer I
- Mad10trunc-His – wash with loading buffer
- Mad10trunc-His – flow through
- Mad10trunc-His – soluble fraction of the crude extract
- Mad10trunc-His – insoluble fraction of the crude extract

<Mad10trunc_Urea.tif> shows the SDS-PAGE (18%, reducing conditions) of the purification of His-Mad10trunc and Mad10trunc-His under denaturing conditions (Fig. S13). The following samples were loaded from top to bottom:

- His-Mad10trunc – insoluble fraction of the crude extract
- His-Mad10trunc – soluble fraction of the crude extract
- His-Mad10trunc – flow through
- His-Mad10trunc – wash with loading buffer
- His-Mad10trunc – washing buffer I
- His-Mad10trunc – washing buffer II
- His-Mad10trunc – eluted protein
- size marker (New England Biolabs, P7719S)
- Mad10trunc-His – eluted protein
- Mad10trunc-His – washing buffer II
- Mad10trunc-His – washing buffer I
- Mad10trunc-His – wash with loading buffer
- Mad10trunc-His – flow through
- Mad10trunc-His – soluble fraction of the crude extract
- Mad10trunc-His – insoluble fraction of the crude extract

4. Quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation (QCMD)

Screening for magnetite-binding was performed with a quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation (QCMD). The measurements were performed with the 4-channel system QSense Analyzer (Biolin Scientific), using commercially available sensor chips (LOT Quantum Design). To account for possible variations between the magnetite coating of the sensor chips, the measurements were set up such that each protein was tested in at least two different channels with different magnetite sensor chips.

The QCMD folder contains the subfolder <IndividualMadProteins>. This folder is a collection of all measurements performed with the individual sfGFP-Mad-His fusion proteins, incl. the sfGFP-His control protein. The respective folders carry the name of each respective fusion protein in the form <sfGFP-Mad-His> or <sfGFP-His>, respectively. The measurement was performed in triplicate and the measurements are numbered from 1-3. The respective data files are labelled <Measurement_number> (e.g. Measurement1). The corresponding data is shown in Fig. S21-S27.

The frequency and dissipation signals were exported for the harmonics 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 (with the exception of sfGFP-Mad10-His, where only the harmonics 1-9 were considered). All data exported from the measurement software was saved as a .txt file.

The folder further contains the subfolder <Mad10SpecificityTest>, which includes the following measurements:

- For the measurement <sfGFP-His_sfGFP-Mad10-His_sequential>, a sensor chip first incubated with sfGFP-His was subsequently flushed with sfGFP-Mad10-His.
- For the measurement <sfGFP-Mad10-His_sfGFP-His_sequential>, the sensor chip was first incubated with sfGFP-Mad10-His and then with sfGFP-His.
- For the measurement <sfGFP-Mad-His_mixture>, the proteins sfGFP-Mad3-His, sfGFP-Mad4-His, sfGFP-Mad5-His, sfGFP-Mad8-His and sfGFP-Mad10-His were co-incubated on the sensor surface.

These measurements were carried out in duplicate. The respective data files are labelled <Measurement_number> (e.g. Measurement1). The corresponding data is shown in Fig. S28 and S29. Again, the frequency and dissipation signals were exported for the harmonics 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13. All data exported from the measurement software was saved as a .txt file.

5. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed at the μ -Spot beam line of the BESSY II synchrotron (Helmholtz-Centrum Berlin). The samples were prepared in the following way: a Kapton film (Breitlander GmbH) was placed into a sample holder, which contained 54 holes covered by the film. For each hole, 10 μ l of the nanoparticle suspension were dropped onto the Kapton film. Further, an α -quartz standard (SiO₂; 1878a; NIST) was added to the Kapton film and used as XRD standard. The suspensions dried on the film and the sample holder was mounted in a sample-detector distance of approximately 180 mm. The samples were measured with a 100 μ m beam in transmission mode. The wavelength was set to 0.826 Å, using a Si111 monochromator. An Eiger X 9M detector (Dectris) was used. The exposure time was set to be between 10-180 s, depending on the signal intensity.

The data reported in the manuscript show the results of MNP synthesis reactions that were performed with a protein concentration of 0.5 μ M (as well as protein-free control reactions). In total, 3-4 different reactions (I-IV) were performed. Each sample was measured in duplicate (multiread mode). The duplicate measurements are labelled <000001> and <000002> and the resulting multiread corrected file is termed <multireadcorr>. The sample and file names as well

as the respective measurement conditions are listed in the tables below (sorted by measurement and sample holder). The file names are organized as <SampleHolder_ScanNumber_..._.tif>, for example <sh1_ScnNr000025_data_000001_000001.tif>.

For data analysis, the DPDAK software (<https://confluence.desy.de/display/DPDAK>; version v1.3.0) was used. The raw files provided here represent .tif files that were exported from the DPDAK software. The multiread corrected files were used for analysis. The exact sample-to-detector distance was calculated using the α -quartz standard. The position of the magnetite (311) peak was used for further lattice parameter calculations and the XRD diffractogram was compared with a magnetite reference provided by the German Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM). The instrumental peak broadening and the full-width-at-half-maximum (FWHM) of the magnetite (311) peak were determined by fitting the (311) peak with a pseudo-Voigt function. The mean crystallite diameter was determined using the Scherrer equation and the corrected FWHM.

Measurement 1 - 15.03.2018				
Sample holder 1				
Row	Hole	Sample	Scan number	Measurement time in seconds
B	1	NIST	25 and 26	20 and 120
B	2	BAM Magnetite	27	60
B	3	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 2h	28	180
B	4	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 4h	30	60
B	5	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 6h	31	60
B	6	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 2h	32	120
B	7	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 4h	34	120
B	8	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 6h	35	60
B	9	NIST	36	60
B	10	empty		
B	11	empty		
B	12	empty		
B	13	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 2h	43	120
B	14	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 4h	44	120
B	15	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 6h	45	60
B	16	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 2h	47	120
B	17	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 4h	48	120
B	18	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 6h	49	60
C	1	empty		
C	2	empty		
C	3	screw		
C	4	empty		
C	5	empty		
C	6	empty		
C	7	screw		
C	8	empty		
C	9	empty		
C	10	empty		
C	11	screw		
C	12	control, synthesis I, 2h	58	120
C	13	control, synthesis I, 4h	59	60
C	14	control, synthesis I, 6h	60	60
C	15	screw		
C	16	NIST	62	120
C	17	empty		
C	18	empty		

Measurement 1 - 15.03.2018				
Sample holder 2				
Row	Hole	Sample	Scan number	Measurement time in seconds
A	1	screw		
A	2	empty		
A	3	BAM magnetite	86	60
A	4	empty		
A	5	screw		
A	6	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 µM, synthesis I, 1h	89	60
A	7	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 µM, synthesis I, 3h	90	60
A	8	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 µM, synthesis I, 5h	91	60
A	9	screw		
A	10	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 µM, synthesis II, 1h	93	60
A	11	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 µM, synthesis II, 3h	94	60
A	12	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 µM, synthesis II, 5h	95	60
A	13	screw		
A	14	empty		
A	15	empty		
A	16	empty		
A	17	screw		
A	18	NIST	101	60
B	1	sfGFP-His 0.5 µM, synthesis I, 1h	102	60
B	2	sfGFP-His 0.5 µM, synthesis I, 3h	103	60
B	3	sfGFP-His 0.5 µM, synthesis I, 5h	104	60
B	4	sfGFP-His 0.5 µM, synthesis II, 1h	105	60
B	5	sfGFP-His 0.5 µM, synthesis II, 3h	106	60
B	6	sfGFP-His 0.5 µM, synthesis II, 5h	107	60
B	7	empty		
B	8	empty		
B	9	NIST	110	60
B	10	empty		
B	11	control, synthesis I, 1h	112	60
B	12	control, synthesis I, 3h	113	60
B	13	control, synthesis I, 5h	114	60
B	14	empty		
B	15	empty		
B	16	empty		
B	17	empty		
B	18	empty		
C	1	NIST	120	60

Measurement 2 - 04.07.2018 and 05.07.2018				
Sample holder 1				
Row	Hole	Sample	Scan number	Measurement time in seconds
A	1	screw		
A	2	empty		
A	3	empty		
A	4	empty		
A	5	screw		
A	6	empty		
A	7	empty		
A	8	empty		
A	9	screw		
A	10	empty		
A	11	empty		
A	12	empty		
A	13	screw		
A	14	empty		
A	15	empty		
A	16	empty		
A	17	screw		
A	18	NIST	527 and 528	120
B	1	empty		
B	2	empty		
B	3	empty		
B	4	empty		
B	5	empty		
B	6	empty		
B	7	empty		
B	8	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 1h	543	120
B	9	NIST	545	120
B	10	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 2h	547	120
B	11	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 3h	549	120
B	12	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 4h	551	120
B	13	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 5h	553	120
B	14	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis I, 6h	555	120
B	15	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 1h	557	120
B	16	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 2h	559	120
B	17	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 3h	561	120
B	18	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 4h	563	120
C	1	NIST	565	120
C	2	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 5h	567	120
C	3	screw		
C	4	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis II, 6h	571	120
C	5	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 1h	573	120
C	6	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 2h	575	120
C	7	screw		
C	8	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 3h	579	120
C	9	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 4h	581	120
C	10	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 5h	583	120
C	11	screw		
C	12	sfGFP-Mad10-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 6h	587	120
C	13	empty		
C	14	empty		
C	15	screw		
C	16	empty		
C	17	empty		
C	18	empty		

Measurement 2 - 04.07.2018 and 05.07.2018				
Sample holder 2				
Row	Hole	Sample	Scan number	Measurement time in seconds
A	1	screw		
A	2	empty		
A	3	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 1h	240	60
A	4	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 3h	241	60
A	5	screw		
A	6	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 5h	243	60
A	7	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis IV, 1h	244	60
A	8	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis IV, 3h	245	60
A	9	screw		
A	10	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis, IV 5h	247	
A	11	empty		
A	12	empty		
A	13	screw		
A	14	empty		
A	15	empty		
A	16	empty		
A	17	screw		
A	18	NIST	255	
B	1	empty		
B	2	empty		
B	3	empty		
B	4	empty		
B	5	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 1h	260	60
B	6	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 3h	261	60
B	7	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis III, 5h	262	60
B	8	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis IV, 1h	263	60
B	9	NIST	264	60
B	10	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis IV, 3h	265	60
B	11	sfGFP-His 0.5 μ M, synthesis IV, 5h	266	60
B	12	empty		
B	13	empty		
B	14	empty		
B	15	empty		
B	16	empty		
B	17	empty		
B	18	empty		
C	1	NIST	274	60
C	2	empty		
C	3	screw		
C	4	empty		
C	5	control, synthesis II, 1h	278	60
C	6	control, synthesis II, 3h	279	60
C	7	screw		
C	8	control, synthesis II, 5h	280	60
C	9	control, synthesis III, 1h	282	60
C	10	control, synthesis III, 3h	283	60
C	11	screw		
C	12	control, synthesis III, 5h	285	60
C	13	control, synthesis IV, 1h	286	60
C	14	control, synthesis IV, 3h	287	60
C	15	screw		
C	16	control, synthesis IV, 5h	289	60
C	17	empty		
C	18	empty		

Measurement 2 - 04.07.2018 and 05.07.2018				
Sample holder 6				
Row	Hole	Sample	Scan number	Measurement time in seconds
A	1	screw		
A	2	empty		
A	3	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μM, synthesis III, 2h	9	60
A	4	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μM, synthesis III, 4h	10	60
A	5	screw		
A	6	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μM, synthesis III, 6h	11	60
A	7	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μM, synthesis IV, 2h	12	60
A	8	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μM, synthesis IV, 4h	13	60
A	9	screw		
A	10	sfGFP-Mad10trunc-His 0.5 μM, synthesis IV, 6h	14	60
A	11	empty		
A	12	empty		
A	13	screw		
A	14	empty		
A	15	empty		
A	16	empty		
A	17	screw		
A	18	NIST	23	120
B	1	empty		
B	2	empty		
B	3	empty		
B	4	empty		
B	5	sfGFP-His 0.5 μM, synthesis III, 2h	30	60
B	6	sfGFP-His 0.5 μM, synthesis III, 4h	32	60
B	7	sfGFP-His 0.5 μM, synthesis III, 6h	33	60
B	8	sfGFP-His 0.5 μM, synthesis IV, 2h	35	60
B	9	NIST	37	120
B	10	sfGFP-His 0.5 μM, synthesis IV, 4h	38	60
B	11	sfGFP-His 0.5 μM, synthesis IV, 6h	39	60
B	12	empty		
B	13	empty		
B	14	empty		
B	15	empty		
B	16	empty		
B	17	empty		
B	18	empty		
C	1	NIST	52	120
C	2	empty		
C	3	screw		
C	4	empty		
C	5	control, synthesis II, 2h	56	60
C	6	control, synthesis II, 4h	57	60
C	7	screw		
C	8	control, synthesis II, 6h	58	60
C	9	control, synthesis III, 2h	59	60
C	10	control, synthesis III, 4h	60	60
C	11	screw		
C	12	control, synthesis III, 6h	61	60
C	13	control, synthesis IV, 2h	62	60
C	14	control, synthesis IV, 4h	63	60
C	15	screw		
C	16	control, synthesis IV, 6h	65	60
C	17	empty		
C	17	empty		
C	18	empty		